

Appendix 1: A brief history of institutionalizing engineering ethics in the US¹

While engineering was born in France (Davis, 1996), engineering ethics emerged in the United States. This country is regarded as a leader in engineering ethics, particularly in the professional approach. The volume of academic conferences, publications, and papers on engineering ethics that are published in the US and translated into other languages demonstrates the significance of this country in the development of engineering ethics. Considering this, it is crucial to comprehend how and why engineering ethics evolved in the United States. [This paragraph could be shifted to Introduction]

The origins of engineering ethics in the US date back to the 1970s and earlier. Before this, several professional engineering societies existed since the beginning of the 20th century, and several engineering codes of conduct were adopted or even revised (Didier, introduction). These societies were founded in the late 19th century in response to concerns about the competence of individuals practicing engineering and public safety in increasingly important engineering projects. Mitcham and Briggie (2009) believe that these societies were patterned by the British model of non-governmental organizations in the nineteenth century. Their objective was to establish and uphold professional standards, disseminate technical knowledge, and advance the interests of the engineering community. The initial codes of conduct were crafted to harmonize the professional engineering community within the country.

In the first decade of the early 20th century, the realization of the necessity for regulatory measures to ensure practitioners' qualifications led to the enactment of laws in some states that oversee engineering practice. It took around forty years for the engineering statutes to be adopted in the remaining states (Musselman, 2011). Subsequently, states instituted licensing boards endowed with the authority to define standards for professional practice, conduct examinations, and issue licenses. During the 1920s, the State Boards of Engineering Examiners coalesced to form the National Council of Examiners for Engineering and Surveying. By 1933, the inaugural Model Engineering Practice Act was conceived by the National Council of State Boards of Engineering Examiners, now known as NCEES. This act served as a prototype for state legislation, furnishing a structure for licensing requirements, examinations, and ethical standards. Two years later, representatives from professional engineering associations joined to establish the National Society of Professional Engineers (NSPE), a nationwide organization for licensed professional engineers committed to

¹ This text is an appendix of the paper "A Comparative Institutional Analysis of Engineering Ethics in the Netherlands and the United States".

addressing the profession's non-technical concerns. This society directed its attention to legislative matters, public comprehension and acknowledgment of the profession, equitable compensation, ethical practice, and safeguarding Professional Engineers (PEs) from endeavors to restrict their right to practice engineering. In its initial years, the NSPE adopted the Canons of Ethics for Engineers and Rules of Professional Conduct.

Subsequently, states underwent modifications to engineering licensing statutes, introducing provisions commonly referred to as industrial exemptions. These state-specific laws delineate circumstances under which engineers can engage in professional practice without holding a license. The exemptions encompass various scenarios: (1) engineers working under the direct supervision of a licensed professional assuming responsibility for their endeavors; (2) engineers employed by public utilities; (3) engineers in the service of the federal government; (4) engineers employed by state government entities; and (5) "in-house" engineers employed by manufacturing or other business enterprises, a category commonly termed the "industrial exemption." Consequently, approximately two-thirds of engineers found themselves excluded from mandatory licensure. However, these exemption laws have not been immune to criticism (Spinden, 2014).

In education, Before the 1970s, certain academic courses that addressed the ethical and moral aspects of science and technology had already been established. However, there have been few courses that discuss ethics in the engineering profession (Baum,1980). In general, when technology was viewed as value-free in the scientific society, ethical studies were not considered essential. With new challenges to this theory in the early 1970s and, of course, the financial support of centers such as the National Science Foundation (NSF), ethical studies of science and engineering began and boomed. The origins of these studies can be traced back to the STS movement, which grew at the time in response to the Vietnam War and environmental concerns. These new studies focused primarily on the effects of new technologies on society; however, as the demand for social accountability from engineering grew, these studies shifted to ethical considerations of engineering practice (Hollander & Steneck, 1990). However, what was the cause of this public demand?

The engineering ethics authors linked some events to this requirement, including consumer and environmental movements, Watergate, the atomic bomb in the Second World War, and several scandals in engineering society, such as the faked testing of Goodrich A-7D air brakes and the Ford Pinto's exploding gas tank. Some considered corruption, inadequacies, or improprieties in different areas of society as the cause of new attention to ethics in the 1970s [1]. However, Davis (1990) believes that although these factors may have been effective, the reason for the ethics boom of the 1970s was the ethics bust in the previous decades. "Ethics, like business, has its ups and downs. We are up now because we were

down”. In fact, in his view, the country had experienced an ethics boom since the 1970s because of the past disregard for ethics in necessary contexts, such as education or professions. We agree with Johnson and Wetmore (2008) that the field of engineering ethics in the United States developed in response to increasing social concern about the dangers of technology.

How were the first steps taken in the development of engineering ethics? With the public publication of scandals by the media, this concern was transferred to the public (Baum, 1980). They were asking what was happening in engineering. The government and companies were blamed for these events (Johnson & Wetmore, 2008). The first steps were taken by academic and professional engineers, and such activities were welcomed by other engineers who had faced moral problems. The pioneering courses arose in a range of departments and programs with a single individual’s effort. NSF and NEH (National Endowment for the Humanities) paid attention to this area, funded some programs, and brought together academic engineers and philosophers from across the country in the late 1970s (Weil, 1984). Involving philosophers could lead to more conceptual clarification of issues and formulation of principles to enhance their analysis of engineering ethics problems and to create helpful teaching resources. (Mitcham and Briggie, 2009). Two research centers at Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute (RPI) and the Illinois Institute of Technology (IIT) gave some philosophers the resources to innovate new courses and initiate research in the late 1970s. Beginning in 1977, the Hasting Centre, with the support of the Rockefeller Brothers Fund and the Carnegie Corporation of New York, undertook a systematic study of the teaching of ethics in higher education, such as engineering (Baum, 1980). As a result, scholars from engineering and philosophy joined to identify and address ethical problems. Several humanists and social scientists from a range of other disciplines – law, social, and management sciences- also contributed and began to become involved in activities dealing with engineering ethics, including the development of new courses, in collaboration both with engineering faculty and in the basic humanities and social sciences disciplines (Baum, 1980). In 1976, NSPE published a report about courses that discussed professionalism. In this report, NSPE made specific recommendations concerning including courses on professionalism in engineering curricula. Engineers were recommended to run the course, and most, if not all, visiting lecturers should be engineering faculty or non-academic engineers. As a response to these projects and the interest they generated, many institutions were introducing new courses. As of 1979, probably thirty to forty such courses were offered (Baum, 1980).

In addition to research and education, several professional associations with special vigor adopted new codes or revised old ones during this decade (Mitcham & Briggie, 2009). For instance, the ECPD revised the canons in 1974 (Baum, 1980). According to Mitcham, the first

steps in developing engineering ethics in this decade started with formulating new codes of conduct by professional societies rather than with education and research to respond to public concern and the importance of engineering in society (Mitcham & Briggie, 2009).

In the 1980s, the publication of engineering ethics studies grew dramatically (Davis, 1990). In 1980, the accrediting organization for engineering curricula, the ECPD, considered formally requiring a course on ethics and professionalism in all accredited engineering curricula (Baum). The first textbooks were published at the beginning of this decade with the support of the NSF (Zandvoort et al., 2000). Only during the first three years of this decade were three significant textbooks authored with the assistance of federal government agencies (Mitcham, 2009). Ethics increasingly gained acceptance as a compulsory or elective part of the engineering curricula. Nevertheless, making engineering ethics compulsory in engineering education was a challenging issue. For instance, only about 20% of engineering students had to follow an ethics-related course (Herkert, 2000).

New books were also released throughout the 1990s, along with new textbook editions. The new *Journal of Science and Engineering Ethics* was the only place articles could be published after it was established. Professional engineering societies hold meetings on recent developments in the discipline. The Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET) engineering criteria 2000 stipulated that institutions must demonstrate eleven outcomes, one of which states that their students must attain “an understanding of professional and ethical responsibility” to be accredited (Mitcham, 1998). This was done in response to concerns raised due to the slow institutionalization of engineering ethics in engineering education. As a result, new courses and programs have been created, which has led to the development of new materials (Johnson & Wetmore, 2008).

New subjects and scopes in engineering ethics started to emerge in the 2000s. Various perspectives and fresh ideas were used to examine ethical issues. The public’s perception of engineering and the value-laden nature of design are two examples of these subjects. Johnson and Wetmore (2008) state that this development resulted from European scholars’ approach to connecting STS and engineering ethics. They asserted that the fundamental connections between these two fields were socio-technical systems and the relationship between technology and society. However, Herkert (2005) attributes these adaptations to the new ideas of 1990s authors in the US.